

N3C Tenant Pilot User Code of Conduct

Version History

Version	Description of changes
All versions	doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10668761 This DOI represents all versions and will always resolve to the latest one.
v1.0 2024-02-10	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• First draft

N3C Tenant Pilot Data Enclave is an NIH clinical data sharing resource, operated under a contract, containing EHR-derived data from individuals who have received longitudinal care from contributing organizations, to support a pilot project evaluating the feasibility of developing of such data enclave access at scale. The N3C Tenant Pilot Data Enclave will leverage the knowledge and capabilities in the centralized curation and large-scale data harmonization created for the NCATS National COVID Cohort Collaborative (N3C).

The N3C Tenant Pilot User Code of Conduct articulates fundamental actions and prohibitions on data user activities involving data or other resources accessible through the N3C Tenant Pilot Data Enclave and reflects the data use terms and conditions outlined in the **Participation Agreement** entered into by Accessing Institutions and NCATS. Failure to abide by any term within this Code of Conduct may result in revocation of approved access to the N3C Tenant Pilot Data Enclave, potentially including any analyses in progress.

Investigators approved by the relevant N3C Tenant Pilot Data Access Committee (DAC) to access and use tenant data within the N3C Tenant Pilot Data Enclave agree to:

1. Use data only for the research projects or comparative studies defined in the Participation Agreement approved by the data-contributing organizations and NCATS.
2. Comply with any applicable local, state, federal, or tribal laws, regulations, or policies with regard to data use, data privacy, and data security and exercise responsible stewardship of data, software, or other tools contained within or uploaded to the N3C Tenant Pilot Data Enclave.
3. Make no attempt to identify institutions, communities, or identifiable populations associated with particular N3C Tenant Pilot data; to re-identify or contact individuals, their relatives, or relevant groups from whom data represented within the N3C Tenant Pilot Data Enclave were collected; or to generate information that could allow individual identities to be readily ascertained.
 - a. Specifically, users will be asked to attest that they understand that the N3C Tenant Pilot datasets contain no Tribal affiliation data and that the use of American Indian or Alaska Native (AI/AN) data and ZIP code information to make assumptions about Tribal affiliation is **not valid or permitted**.
4. Maintain the confidentiality of the data accessible within the enclave and not distribute, not provide access to, not attempt to download, or otherwise capture views of N3C Tenant Pilot data for use or disclosure to any entity or individual beyond those specified in the project specified in the Participation Agreement.

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5. Publicly disseminate findings based on research conducted using the N3C Tenant Pilot Data Enclave, ideally through open-access formats. And, as applicable, enable the development of new diagnostic, therapeutic, or other interventions to benefit public health.
6. Provide appropriate acknowledgment of the NCATS and the N3C Tenant Pilot Data Enclave and any relevant algorithms or software utilized within the enclave in any dissemination of research findings, analyses or tool development Abide by the **Attribution and Publication Principles** and the **Community Guiding Principles** for the N3C Tenant Pilot.
7. Report any Data Access Incident as defined in the Participation Agreement within 2 business days after discovery by the User or the Accessing Institution to NCATS by emailing NCATSDataAccessIncidents@nih.gov (link sends e-mail).
8. Respect the tenets represented in this Code of Conduct and the terms and conditions of the Participation Agreement by upholding these commitments beyond the expiration of any approved Data Use Requests.